

The Diatom Flora of Waghur Dam, Jalgaon, Maharashtra

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ABSTRACT:

The study focused on evaluating the taxonomic details and geographic distribution of the periphytic genera *Achnanthes*, *Amphora*, *Diploneis*, *Gomphonema*, *Mastogloia*, *Navicula*, *Pinnularia*, *Fragilaria*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Cymbella* and *Synedra* in various parts of Waghur Dam. Over the course of three years from January 2022 to December 2024, samples were gathered from multiple sites around the Waghur Dam. Findings include the identification of 01 species of *Amphora*, *Diploneis*, *Gomphonema*, *Mastogloia*, 12 species of *Navicula*, 05 species of *Pinnularia* & *Anomoeoneis*, 04 species of *Fragilaria*, 03 species of *Achnanthes* and *Stauroneis*, 02 species of *Cymbella* and *Synedra* all of which were documented for the first time in this location. The highest diversity of these species was observed during the winter, followed by the monsoon and summer seasons. The physicochemical parameters of the Waghur Dam water were found to be highly conducive for the growth of these taxa. This research underscores the potential of using *Achnanthes*, *Amphora*, *Diploneis*, *Gomphonema*, *Mastogloia*, *Navicula*, *Pinnularia*, *Fragilaria*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Cymbella* and *Synedra* as biological indicators in freshwater ecosystems.

Keyword: - Diatoms, Bacillariophyceae, Waghur Dam, Jalgaon district, Maharashtra.

INTRODUCTION:

Waghur Dam is an earthfill dam located on the Waghur river near Kandari and Varadsim, Jalgaon district in Indian state of Maharashtra. The Waghur river flows from its source near Ajanta through the Khandesh region. The dam main purpose is to supply water for irrigation purpose in downstream area. A preliminary survey of algae in the Waghur Dam was conducted at various sites during the years 2022–2024. The study revealed the presence of numerous planktonic algae in the water body. Several taxa of freshwater algae were recorded from different locations along the Waghur Dam. The dominant species observed at certain sites during the winter season included *Achnanthes*, *Navicula*, *Pinnularia*, *Fragilaria*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Synedra* and *Cymbella*.

The present work represents a significant systematic study on the algal diversity of the Waghur Dam. This investigation is an outcome of broader biodiversity studies focused on the freshwater algae of the region and contributes to our understanding of the algal flora in this area. Accordingly, the study of the aquatic vegetation was undertaken during the years 2022–2024.

During the study, a large number of phytoplankton's like *Achnanthes*, *Amphora*, *Diploneis*, *Gomphonema*, *Mastogloia*, *Navicula*, *Pinnularia*, *Fragilaria*, *Stauroneis*, *Anomoeoneis*, *Cymbella* and *Synedra* were observed. However, the algal flora of Waghur Dam has not been studied so far and this is the first report. For the present study, different locations of the Waghur Dam water body were selected. The water samples from each locality were collected once in a month in the morning between 8.00 a.m. to 11.00 a.m. The collections were made for 3 years during 2022-2024, during the months of November to March. For phytoplankton analysis, water samples were collected by plankton net, as per the method adopted by Narkhede (2006). 20 liters of surface water was collected (by standing in the back water of dam at about 100-120 cm depth) by dipping a jug and filtered through the plankton net and was collected in 1 lit. wide mouth bottle, 30 ml of water sample was preserved in 4% formalin. The morphological studies of specimens were done by using Olympus Research Microscope and Labomed Microscope and the photographs were taken using Kodak EazyShare cx 7330 cameras. Identification of taxa was done using Fritsch (1935), Patel and George (1977), Philipose (1967), Prescott (1951), Rath and Adhikari (2005) and other relevant literature.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Algal samples from each site were collected once a month in the morning, between 8:00 a.m. and 10:00 a.m., during the years 2022 to 2024. Samples were collected in 100 ml capacity bottles and transported to the laboratory. For preservation and further taxonomic investigation, the samples were transferred to 20 ml capacity bottles containing 4% formalin. For the collection of macroalgae, 1000 ml capacity bottles were used, and the preservation method was the same as described above. Phytoplankton samples were collected using a plankton net, following the method described by Narkhede (2006). Twenty liters of surface water from the Godavari River (at a depth of approximately 100–120 cm) were collected by dipping a jug about 3 cm below the surface. The collected water was filtered through the plankton net, and the concentrate was stored in a 1-liter wide-mouth bottle. In the laboratory, 20 ml of the sample was preserved in 4% formalin, as previously described.

1. *Achnanthes lanceolata* (Breb.) Grun. (Pl.1, fig. 1)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 56 (Pl. 5, fig 116 b)

Valves 10.8-15 μ long, 4.1-5 μ broad, elliptical lanceolate with ends broadly rounded and flat; raphe valve with thin threadlike raphe; axial area narrow, linear; central area broad, quadrate; striae 18-20 in 10 μ , strong, radial; rapheless valve with narrow, lanceolate pseudoraphe; horse shoe shaped marking on one side in the center; striae 18-19 in 10 μ .

2. *A. lanceolata* (Breb.) Grun. v. *rostrata* Hustedt (Pl. 1, fig. 2)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 56 (Pl. 5, fig 118 a)

Valves 9-11 μ long, 4.8 – 5 μ broad, elliptic lanceolate with constricted produced, very slightly capitate ends; raphe valve with thin and straight raphe; axial area narrow; central area small; striae 12- 14 in 10 μ , strong, slightly wider; rapheless valves with narrow pseudoraphe, slightly wider in the middle; a clear horse shoe shape marking on one side of central area; striae 12 in 10 μ .

3. *A. minutissima* (Kuetz.) Grun. (Pl. 1, fig. 3)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 58 (Pl 5, fig 122b)

Frutules small, linear and bent in girdle view; valves 19-32 μ long, 3-3.7 μ broad, narrow, linear lanceolate with broadly rounded ends; axial area narrow; central area slightly wider on raphe valve; striae 24-26 in 10 μ , fine.

4. *Amphora coffeaeformis* Agardh v. *bhusavalensis* v.nov. (Pl. 1, fig. 4)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 160 (Pl. 19, fig 430)

Frustules elliptic lanceolate, 15-20 μ long, 7-9 μ broad; valves 15-20 μ long, 3.8-4.4 μ broad, arcuate on the dorsal margin and slightly concave or more or less straight ventral margin; ends constricted on dorsal side, slightly constricted on ventral side and beak like, ventrally directed; raphe thin, more or less straight, slightly directed to the ventral side towards the ends; striae about 22-24 in 10 μ , clearly punctate in the middle and indistinct towards the ends; ventral side structureless.

5. *Anomoeneis brachysira* (Breb.) Grun. V. *genuina* A. Cl. (Pl. 1, fig. 5)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 96 (Pl. 11, fig 231)

Valves 14- 18.6 μ long 4-4.6 μ broad, rhombic lanceolate with slightly produced attenuated ends; raphe thin and straight with distinct central pores and very slightly curved terminal fissures; axial area very narrow; central area wider; striae about 30 in 10 μ , very fine, irregularly interrupted by longitudinal wavy, hyaline bands.

6. *A. brachysira* (Breb.) Grun. V. *thermalis* (Grun.) (Pl. 1, fig. 6)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 96 (Pl. 11, fig 232)

Valves 12- 19 μ long, 4- 5.3 μ broad, linear lanceolate with produced, slightly constricted, capitate ends; raphe thin and straight with central pores distinct and terminal fissures very slightly curved; axial area narrow; central area somewhat large; striae about 30 in 10 μ , very fine and difficulty seen, interrupted by longitudinal hyaline bands.

7. *A. exilis* (Kuetz. Grun) Cleve (Pl. 1, fig. 7)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 97 (Pl. 11, fig 233)

Valves 23.9– 24.6 μ long, 4-4.6 μ broad, narrow, lanceolate with capitate rounded ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area very narrow; central area small, rounded or elliptical; striae about 30 in 10 μ radial, finely punctate, crossed by several longitudinal hyaline ribs, 12 – 13 in 10 μ , irregularly formed.

8. *A. lanceolata* Gandhi (Pl. 1, fig. 8)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 97 (Pl. 11, fig. 235)

Valves 48- 62 μ long, 14 – 6 μ broad, somewhat broadly lanceolate, robust with rostrate ends; raphe thin and straight with prominent central pores and curved terminal fissures; axial area narrow, linear; central area large, unilateral; striae 18-20 in 10 μ , slightly radial, coarsely punctate, crossed by many hyaline longitudinal irregular spaces.

9. *A. santapaui* sp.nov. (Pl. 1, fig. 9)

Sarode and Kamt 1984 P. 97 (Pl. 11, fig 240)

Valves 14.6 – 18 μ long, 4.4 – 6 μ broad, broadly lanceolate to elliptic lanceolate with constricted, shortly capitate ends; raphe thin and straight with central pores closely set; axial area very narrow; central area small, rounded; striae 18-20 in 10 μ , perpendicular to the middle line and interrupted by longitudinal hyaline bands.

10. *Cymbella gonzalvesii* sp. nov. (Pl. 1, fig. 10)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 169 (Pl. 21, fig 482)

Valves 30-39.5 μ long 6-7.2 μ broad nearly lanceolate dorsal margin convex and ventral margin slightly convex, ends rounded; raphe thick and almost straight, excentric; axial area moderate linear; central area large, unilateral; striae 14 -16 in 10 μ radial.

11. *C. vidarbhensis* sp. nov. (Pl. 1, fig. 11)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 179 (Pl 21, fig 480)

Valves 61-78 μ long, 16-17 μ broad, lunate, dorsal margin strongly convex and slightly depressed towards both the ends; ventral margin almost straight and ventrally gibbous; ends rounded; raphe strongly excentric; straight with terminal fissures ventrally directed; axial area moderate, linear; central area small; striae 9-10 in 10 μ , strong and coarse, radial throughout.

12. *Diploneis puella* (Schum) Cleve (Pl. 1, fig. 12)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 87 (Pl. 10, fig. 205)

Valves 12-18.2 μ long, 6.5 -7.8 μ broad, elliptic with rounded ends, valve surface costate; costae 13-14 in 10 μ , thick and distinct, continued into the furrows as large alveoli; central nodule large dilated.

13. *Fragilaria brevistriata* Grun. v. *vidarbhensis* v. nov. (Pl. 1, fig. 13)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 26(Pl. 1, fig. 18 b)

Frustules linear, loosely attached together to form short chains in girdle view; valves 19.7- 23 μ long, 3.5 -4.8 μ broad, linear lanceolate, strongly tumid in the middle and slightly inflated towards the ends with somewhat acutely rounded ends; pseudoraphe broad in middle, linear lanceolate; striae 11-13 in 10 μ , thick.

14. *F. capucina* Desm. v. *arctica* A. Cl. (Pl 1, fig. 14)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P.26 (Pl 1, fig. 19)

Valves 26-35 μ long, 2.9 – 3.5 μ broad, slender, sub – linear, narrow towards the ends; ends slightly constricted; pseudoraphe distinct, linear lanceolate; central not formed; striae 16- 18 in 10 μ .

15. *F. rumpens* (Kuetz.) Carl. V. *fragilarioides* (Grun.) A. Cl. (Pl. 1, fig. 16)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 28 (Pl. 1, fig 27)

Frustules in continuous chains; valves 30.5 – 32 μ long, 3-3.5 μ broad, linear lanceolate with constricted slightly capitate ends; pseudoraphe narrow; central area large; striae 12- 14 in 10 μ , coarse and distinct.

16. *F. virescens* Ralfs v. *capitata* Krasske (Pl. 1, fig. 16)

S.N. Nandan, M.D. Pawar and K.D. Rajput P. 290 (Pl. 1, fig 5)

Valves 113.86 μ m long, 7.4 μ m broad, linear with capitate ends: pseudoraphe narrower, transverse striae fine 12-19 in 10 μ m; central area absent; axial area absent

17. *Gomphonema ventricosum* Gregory (Pl. 1, fig. 17)

Mahajan K.D. & Nandan S.N.2009 P.28 (Pl. 6, fig 3)

Valves 43.7-67.16 μ m long, 10.22-14.7 μ m broad, at the middle towards the head pole strongly narrowed, foot pole more or less round headed, cell wall structure very thick. Middle strips alternate with long and short, valves at the ends flatly rounded; central area not unilaterally expanded to the wall margin, valves more or less oval shaped, atleast at headpole obtusely rounded. Valves without cross constriction at the most the margin is slightly wavy (tribly) or the ends narrowly haeded, striae 11-13 in 10 μ m, canal like.

18. *Mastogloia baltica* Grun. (Pl. 1, fig. 18)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 60 (Pl. 6, fig 128)

Valves 34-47.6 μ long, 12-13.6 μ broad, elliptic lanceolate with produced capitate ends; raphe nearly straight in between two longitudinal ribs; axial area narrow; central area small, roundish; loculi 5-6 in 10 μ ; striae 20-21 in 10 μ , slightly radial and finely punctate.

19. *N. bacillum* (Ehr.) f. *minor* V.H. (Pl. 1, fig. 19)

Sarode and Kamat P1984 P. 103 (Pl. 11, fig 244)

Valves 12-20 μ long, 3.5 – 4.5 μ broad, linear elliptic with almost parallel margins and broadly rounded ends; axial area narrow; central area slightly widened, roundish; striae 18-20 in 10 μ , slightly radial.

20. *N. constans* Hustedt v. *symmetrica* Hustedt (Pl 1, fig. 20)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 106 (Pl 12, fig. 253)

Valves 25.5 -29 μ long, 9.5 – 11.5 μ broad, elliptic lanceolate with constricted, subcapitate ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow; central; central area large, transversely widened; striae 16-17 in 10 μ , radial, long and short striae alternate each other in the centre.

21. *N. cryptocephala* Kuetz. v. *veneta* (Kuetz.) Grun (Pl. 2, fig. 21)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P.107 (Pl. 12, fig. 257)

Valves 21- 31.2 μ long, 5.5- 6.8 μ broad, linear lanceolate with slightly constricted ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow; central area rectangular; striae 12-13 in 10 μ , radial in the middle and convergent at the ends, slightly longer striae alternate with shorter ones in the middle.

22. *N. grimmi* Krasske (Pl 2, fig. 22)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 112 (Pl 13, fig 276)

Valves 19 -25 μ long, 7.1-8.2 μ broad, elliptic lanceolate with constricted capitate ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow; central area large, rectangular; striae 14-15 in 10 μ , radial.

23. *N. halophila* (Grun.) Cleve f. *subcapitata* Ostrup (Pl. 2, fig. 23)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 113(Pl. 13, fig. 278)

Valves 33-40 μ long, 6.7 – 7.5 μ broad, lanceolate with slightly produced and capitate ends; axial area narrow, linear; central area slightly widened in the middle; striae 15-16 in 10 μ , perpendicular to the middle line.

24. *N. maharashtrensis* Sarode Et. Kamat (Pl 2, fig 24)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 114 (Pl 15, fig 338)

Valves 15-17 μ long, 4.8- 5.2 μ broad, very small, rhombic lanceolate with somewhat acutely rounded ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area very narrow; central area small rounded; striae about 28 in 10 μ , very fine and slightly radial.

25. *N. minuta* (Cleve) A. Cl. (Pl 2, fig. 25)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 114/115 (Pl 13, fig 285)

Valves 18.5-21 μ long, 6.2 –7 μ broad, broadly lanceolate with constricted, shortly capitate ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area very narrow; central area small, roundish, striae about 24 in 10 μ strongly radial and fine.

26. *N. protracta* Grun. (Pl. 2, fig. 26)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 117 (Pl. 13, fig 294)

Valves 19.5 – 23 μ long, 6.5 – 7 μ broad, linear or slightly linear elliptical with constricted, broadly rostrate, subtruncate ends; raphe thin and straight with slightly curved terminal fissures; axial area very narrow, linear; central area small, rounded; striae 18-20 in 10 μ , strong and radial.

27. *N. pupula* Kuetz. (Pl. 2, fig. 27)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 117 (Pl.33, fig. 295)

Valves 18.4 – 35.5 μ long, 7.3 – 10.9 μ broad, linear lanceolate or sub-elliptical with broadly rounded and slightly constricted ends; raphe thin and straight; polar areas present; axial area narrow, linear; central area rectangular, transversely widened; striae 16-18 in 10 μ , fine, radial and slightly curved.

28. *N. salinarum* Grun v. *intermedia* (Grun) Cleve (Pl. 2, fig. 28)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 123 (Pl 14, fig. 315)

Valves 29.2 – 35 μ long, 7.8 – 8.2 μ broad, lanceolate with produced capitate ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow, linear; central area moderate; striae 18 – 19 in 10 μ , lineate, radial and curved in the middle and the convergent at the ends; short and long striae alternate in the middle.

29. *N. subrhynchocephala* Hustedt (Pl. 2, fig. 29)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 124 (Pl 14, fig 320)

Valves 32-37 μ long, 8.1 – 9.5 μ broad, lanceolate with produced capitate ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow, linear; central area large, rounded; striae 12-14in 10 μ , slightly radial in the middle and slightly convergent at the ends.

30. *N. tuscula* (Ehr.) Grun (Pl. 2, fig. 30)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P.125 (Pl. 1, fig 323)

Valves 71- 73.5 μ long, 22-23 μ broad, elliptical with strongly capitate ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow, linear; central area large, transversely extended; striae 13-14 in 10 μ , radial throughout, crossed by many longitudinal hyaline bands.

31. *Pinnularia brebissonni* (Kuetz.) Cleve v. *producta* A.Cl. f. *biundulata* (O. Muell.) A.Cl. (Pl. 2, fig. 31)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 138 (Pl. 15, fig. 356)

Valves 31-38 μ long, 6-8 μ broad, linear lanceolate, slightly concave in the middle with constricted, broadly produced, rounded ends; raphe thin, slightly undulated with central pores unilaterally bent and terminal fissures curved; axial area moderately wide, linear lanceolate, central area large, reaching the margins; striae 10-11 in 10 μ , thick, strongly radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

32. *P. finlandica* A. Cl. (Pl. 2, fig. 32)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 142 (Pl. 16, fig 372)

Valves 47-55.7 μ long, 10-11 μ broad, linear with parallel margins and rounded ends; raphe thin and straight with central pores unilaterally bent and terminal fissures curved; axial area wide, linear; central area slightly dilated and somewhat unilateral; striae 10 -12 in 10 μ , coarse, slightly radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

33. *P. kolhapurensis* Gandhi (Pl.2, fig. 33)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 145 (Pl. 17, fig. 381)

Valves 32.5 -37 μ long, 7.5 -8 μ broad, sublinear with feeble convex margins and slightly constricted, produced, truncate rounded ends; raphe thin and straight with unilaterally bent central pores and slightly curved terminal fissures; axial area linear; central area wide, rhomboid, reaching the margins; striae thick, 12-13 in 10 μ , radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

34. *P. lundii* Hustedt. (Pl. 2, fig. 34)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 146 (Pl. 17, fig. 386)

Valves 38-52 μ long, 9-11 μ broad, linear lanceolate or linear elliptical with constricted, broadly capitate rounded ends; raphe thin and straight with central pores unilaterally bent and terminal fissures curved; axial area moderate, narrowly lanceolate; central area wide, reaching the margins; striae 11-13 in 10 μ , coarse, radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

35. *P. subcapitata* Greg. V. *lapponica* A.Cl. (Pl. 2, fig. 35)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 156 (Pl. 18, fig 417)

Valves 34 – 51.3 μ long, 6.5 7 μ broad, linear with slightly produced, constricted, feebly capitate ends; rephe thin and straight with central pores slightly unilateral bent; axial area wide,

linear; central area large, reaching the margins; striae 11-12 in 10 μ , strong, very slightly radial in the middle and convergent at the ends.

36. *Stauroneis anceps* ehr. V. *amphicephala* (Kuetz.) V.H. (Pl. 2, fig 36)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 90 (Pl. 10, fig 212)

Valves 41.5 – 53 μ long, 10.7- 11 \downarrow 0 broad, linear lanceolate with somewhat suddenly constricted, slightly produce capitate ends; raphe thin and straight, threadlike, central pores distinct; axial area narrow; central area large, stauroid; striae about 25 in 10 μ , indistinctly punctate fine.

37. *S. kirtikarii* sp. Nov. (Pl.2, fig. 37)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 91 (Pl. 11, fig 230)

Valves 32.5-38.5 μ long, 8.1 – 10 μ broad, elliptic to linear elliptic with broadly rostrate, very slightly capitate ends; raphe thin and straight with distinct central pores; axial area narrow; central area large, stauroid, narrowed towards the margins; striae 22-24 in 10 μ , very fine and finely punctate.

38. *S. thermicola* (Boye Pet.) Lund (Pl. 2, fig. 38)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 95 (Pl. 11, fig 229)

Valves 21.5 -23 μ long, 4.5-6 μ broad, linear to linear lanceolate with very slightly constricted, produced, rounded ends; raphe thin and straight; axial area narrow; central area large, a rectangular stauroid widening towards the margins; striae 18-20 in 10 μ in the middle and up to 25 in 10 μ towards the ends.

39. *Synedra tabulata* (Ag.) Kuetz. (Pl. 2, fig. 39)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P.31 (Pl. 2, fig. 36)

Valves 45. 3- 55 μ long, 3-3.4 μ broad, linear, narrow, with tapering rounded ends; pseudoraphe slightly broad; central area absent; striae 12-14 in 10 μ , distinct.

40. *S. ulna* (Nitz.) Ehr. v. *danica* (Kuetz.) Grun. (Pl. 2, fig. 40)

Sarode and Kamat 1984 P. 32/33 (Pl. 2, fig. 40)

Valves 130.6-145 μ long, 3.5 -4.5 μ broad, slender and strongly narrow at the ends with somewhat rounded and capitate ends; striae 9-10 in 10 μ strong, uniformly placed.

PLATE: -1

Fig. 1. *Achnanthes lanceolata* 2. *Achnanthes lanceolata* v. *rostrata*, 3. *Achnanthes minutissima* 4. *Amphora coffeaeformis* v. *bhusavalensis* 5. *Anomoeneis brachysira* v. *genuinea* 6. *Anomoeoneis brachysira* v. *thermalis* 7. *Anomoeoneis exilis* 8. *Anomoeneis lanceolata* 9. *Anomoeoneis santapau* 10. *Cymbella gonzalvesii* 11. *Cymbella vidarbhensis* 12. *Diploneis puella* 13. *Fragilaria brevistriata* v. *vidarbhensis* 14. *Fragilaria capucina* v. *arctica* 15. *Fragilaria rumpens* v. *fragilarioides* 16. *Fragilaria virescens* v. *capitata* 17. *Gomphonema ventricosum* 18. *Mastogloia baltica* 19. *Navicula bacillum* f. *minor* 20. *Navicula constans* v. *symmetrica*

PLATE: -2

Fig. 21. *Navicula cryptocephala* v. *veneta* 22. *Navicula grimmi* 23. *Navicula halophila* f. *subcapitata* 24. *Navicula maharashtrensis* 25. *Navicula minuta* 26. *Navicula protracta* 27. *Navicula pupula* 28. *Navicula salinarum* v. *intermedia* 29. *Navicula subrhynchocephala* 30. *Navicula tuscula* 31. *Pinnularia brebissonni* v. *producta* 32. *Pinnularia finlandica* 33. *Pinnularia kolhapurensis* 34. *Pinnularia lundii* 35. *Pinnularia subcapitata* v. *lapponica* 36. *Stauroneis anceps* v. *amphicephala*, 37 *Stauroneis kirtikarii* 38. *Stauroneis thermicola* 39. *Synedra tabulate* 40. *Synedra ulna* v. *Danica*

Result and Discussion: -

The paper “Diatom Flora of Waghur Dam, Jalgaon, Maharashtra ‘’has been reported with their 12 genus and 40 species of Diatom.

Following are the name of Genus observed in paper with the number of species:

Genus Name	Number of species
1. <i>Achnanthes</i>	3 sp.
2. <i>Amphora</i>	1 sp.
3. <i>Anomoeneis</i>	5 sp.
4. <i>Cymbella</i>	2 sp.
5. <i>Diploneis</i>	1 sp.
6. <i>Fragilaria</i>	4 sp.
7. <i>Gomphonema</i>	1 sp.
8. <i>Mastoglia</i>	1 sp.
9. <i>Navicula</i>	12 sp.
10. <i>Pinnularia</i>	5 sp.
11. <i>Stauroneis</i>	3 sp.
12. <i>Synedra</i>	2 sp.
Total: 12 Genus	40 species.

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